

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

A STUDY OF DRUG-DRUG INTERACTION AMONG INPATIENT IN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL.

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 20/11/2020

Available online

31/12/2020

Keywords

Drug Interaction,
Severity of Interaction,
Mechanism of Interaction,
Disease.

ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: The objective of this study was to identify Drug-Drug Interaction among the inpatient admitted in ICU and the Medical Ward of a tertiary care teaching hospital in India. **METHOD:** This study was a prospective observational study conducted over a period of 6 months from July 2016 to January 2017 among inpatients of ICU and Medical Ward. The prescriptions having 2 or more drug and where DDIs was suspected were selected. The drugs in the prescription were analyzed through drug interaction checker software. The DDIs were classified based on the severity of Interactions, mechanism of interaction, the relation of disease and drug interaction, and the total number of drug prescribed were determined. **RESULT:** There was a total of 225 patients in our study. Out of 225(100%) total patients who had drug-drug interactions, There were a total of 72(32%) patients in ICU and a total of 153(68%) patient in the Medical Ward. An average of 7.625 drugs per prescription was prescribed in ICU and an average of 5.70 drugs per prescription were prescribed in Medical Ward. There were 1333 drug-drug interaction. Among them, 523 DDIs were in ICU and 810 DDIs were in the Medical Ward. A severity assessment showed that in both ICU and Medical ward, majority of interaction were moderate followed by minor interaction. In ICU (57.93%) and in the Medical Ward (62.96%) were moderate drug interaction respectively. On assessing the mechanism of DDIs, pharmacodynamic interaction in ICU were (34.99%) which was higher than pharmacokinetic interaction which was (33.46%) followed by unknown mechanism (31.54%). Whereas in Medical ward most of the interaction was pharmacokinetic Interaction (45.55%) followed by an unknown mechanism (30.74%) and pharmacodynamic interaction (23.70%). Finding of this study showed that cardiovascular disease had (24.28%) and respiratory disease had (18.54%) DDIs in ICU. Similarly, in the Medical Ward cardiovascular disease had (36.79%) and respiratory disease had (23.33%) DDIs. This study result showed that as the number of drug increases in a prescription, the number of DDIs also increases. The management required for DDIs in the study was Dosage adjustment which was 16% followed by monitoring drug level which was 15%. **CONCLUSION:** A significant number of drug interactions were seen in the prescription of the inpatient of ICU and Medical ward. The most prevailing interaction was Moderate interaction which was the highest number followed by minor interaction. Polypharmacy was the major factor responsible for DDIs. This study highlights the need for intense monitoring of patients to help detect and prevent them from serious health hazards associated with DDIs.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr. Jagrit Koirala et al.** A Study of Drug-Drug Interaction Among Inpatient in Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital.. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2020;10(12).

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INTRODUCTION

Drug Interaction can be defined as an alteration in the efficacy or toxicity of one drug due to the presence of another administered drug. Drug-drug Interactions can lead to changes in the systemic exposure of drugs due to alteration in metabolism and excretion which results in loss of efficacy, adverse drug reaction or, toxicity. Drug-drug Interaction can prevail pharmacodynamically and pharmacokinetically. Drug Interaction can be complex and may involve more than one mechanism of interaction for example Induction and inhibition of the same enzyme or transporter, additive effects when multiple inducers and inhibitors are concurrently used, inhibitors used in a patient with liver and kidney disease, and genetic variation in enzymatic activity among patients¹. The potential cause of DDIs is polypharmacy, herbal medication, and OTC medication. Polypharmacy is described as the concurrent use of 5-10 drugs in a single prescription². As the number of drugs in prescription increases, the probability of drug-drug Interaction increases³ although, two drugs in a prescription are probable to have drug interaction. Drug interaction can be life-threatening. Meta-analysis reports state 7% of hospitalization of elderly patients is drug-related⁴.

A study conducted in Switzerland reported that 56.2% of patients were exposed to one or more major or moderate drug interactions in the internal medicine ward⁵. In a literature review, it was found that 0.54% of emergency visits, 0.57% hospital admission, and 0.12% hospital readmission were due to actual DDIs and 4.8% of the elderly admission were due to drug interaction⁶. Herbal drugs are practiced in South Asia for ages. The patient may intake both herbal and allopathic medication, for the disease, at the same time without professional guidance also they may not spontaneously reveal their use when asked medication history. It can cause a serious problem either through their inherent toxicity or by interacting with other allopathic drugs or the herbal drug itself. For example, kava kava (piper methysticum) taken for anxiety was withdrawn from general sale in 2003 after 78 cases of hepatotoxicity related to its use were reported⁷.

Drug-Drug Interaction can cause ADRs. WHO defines an ADR as a response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs in doses normally used for prophylaxis, diagnosis, treatment, or for modification of physiological function⁸. ADRs are a substantial burden on health care worldwide and they are considered the leading cause of morbidity and mortality. ADRs also account for an increase in medical cost and account for 5% - 10% of admission to internal ward⁹. Rational drug therapy can reduce ADRs. Rational prescribing implies proper pharmacological treatment for a proper duration of time with minimum effective dose to a properly diagnosed patient¹⁰. The clinical pharmacist has a major role in preventing Drug-Drug interaction. An Integrated health care system and collaboration with the clinical pharmacist can decrease the health care burden and economy. The direct participation of the pharmacist on clinical settings significantly decreases pharmacy and hospital costs, as well as the length of hospital stay of a patient when compared with minimal participation of the pharmacist¹¹.

This study was designed to assess the prescribed medication to find out the prevalence of drug-drug Interaction; severity of drug-drug Interaction; drug-drug interaction in relation to various diseases

AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

AIM:

To identify drug-drug Interaction among inpatient in a tertiary care teaching hospital through prescription analysis.

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of this study was to identify Drug-Drug Interaction among the inpatient admitted in ICU and the Medical Ward of a tertiary care teaching hospital in India, to assess the prescription to investigate severity and mechanism of interaction total number of drug prescribed to the individual patient and their relation with disease and determination of management for DDIs.

METHODOLOGY:

STUDY SITE:

A prospective observational study was carried out for a period of 6 months from July 2016 - January 2017. The prescription of the inpatient from ICU and internal medicine including male and female ward were analyzed for DDIs. The research was conducted in Sathgiri Medical College and Research Center and NRR Hospital in Bangalore; It was approved by the ethics committee of R.R College of Pharmacy, Bangalore.

STUDY DESIGN:

A Prospective observational study conducted for over six months.

STUDY DURATION:

Six months of study with a data collection period of 3 months and 3 months of prescription analysis for DDIs through drug interaction checker software.

STUDY POPULATION:

The total number of patients was 640 out of which 225(35.16%) patients had drug-drug interaction. 225 Prescription and case sheets of an individual patient were analyzed.

STUDY CRITERIA:**INCLUSION CRITERIA:**

The Inpatient of the Medical Ward and ICU including both men and women who were age above 18 years were included in the study. The prescription of two or more than two drugs was analyzed for drug-drug interactions.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

Patients with a history of Drug abuse, surgical patient, gynecological patient, pediatric patient were excluded from the study.

SOURCE OF DATA:

Patient case sheet, Prescription, Patient medication review chart.

STUDY MATERIALS:

Patient medication review chart, Patient case sheet, drug-drug interactions Documentation form. Drug interaction was checked using the software www.drugs.com. Depending on severity It categorizes interaction as major DDIS, moderate DDIs and, minor DDIs . Other websites like RXlist.com, medscape.com was used as a reference.

Following is the classification of DDIs based on severity:

- 1.Major: Potentially life-threatening; require medical intervention to minimize or prevent the serious adverse effects.
- 2.Moderate: Results in potential deterioration of the patient's clinical condition and may require an alteration in therapy.
- 3.Minor: The effects are usually mild and may not require a change in therapy.

STUDY PROCEDURE:

Patient data were collected in the patient data collection pro forma which includes demographic details of the patient, diagnosis, lab reports, medication.

DDI documentation form was used which includes information such as prescribed medication, drug interaction mechanism categorization, consequence and severity of interaction, drug Interaction Management.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

For categorical variables, the percentage was calculated and continuous variables were expressed as mean. A comparison among subgroups was performed using the student T-test. A chi square test was used to analyze the relationship between gender and the mechanism of DDIs. Statistical Analysis was done using MS Excel and Vassarstat. P value < 0.05% were considered statistically significant.

PATIENT DISTRIBUTION BASED ON GENDER:

Out of 225(100%) total patient included in the study, 145(64.44%) were male and 80(35.55%) were female. These patients were prescribed ≥ 2 drugs in the prescription.

Table 1: Patient distribution based on gender.

Total number of patient (%)	Total number of male patient (%)	Total number of female patient (%)
225 (100 %)	145 (64.44 %)	80 (35.55%)

Fig 1: Pie chart of patient distribution based on gender.

Patient distribution based on their age group

Elderly patients predominated both ICU and Medical Ward of the hospital. Out of 72 patients in ICU, 27(37.5%) patients were in the age group (51-70) and 20(27.77%) were in the age group > 70 years. Out of 153 patient in the Medical Ward, 61(39.86%) were in the age group (31-50) years, and 53(34.64%) patients were in the age group (51-70) years.

Table 2: Patient distribution based on their age group.

Age group of patient (%)	No. of male patient, (%)	No. of female patient, (%)	Total No. of patient, (%)
(ICU)(n=72)			
<30yrs	9(12.5%)	4(5.55%)	13(18.05%)
31-50yrs	7(9.72%)	5(6.94%)	12(16.66%)
51-70 yrs	16(22.22%)	11(15.27%)	27(37.5%)
>70yrs	13(18.05%)	7(9.72%)	20(27.77%)
Medical Ward(n=153)			
<30	17(11.11%)	22(14.37%)	39(17.14%)
31-50	48(31.37%)	13(8.49%)	61(39.86%)
51-70	35(22.87%)	18(11.76%)	53(34.64%)

Total number of patient and drugs.

There were 72(32%) total patients in ICU out of 225(100%) patients included in the study. The total number of male patient was 45(20%) and the female patient was 27(12%). Total drugs prescribed to ICU patients were 549 with an average of 7.625 drugs per prescription. The minimum drug prescribed to patient ranged from 5 drugs per prescription to a maximum of 18 drugs per prescription.

There were 153(68%) patients in the medical ward out of 225(100%).The total number of female patients in medical ward was 53(23.55%) and male patient was 100(44.44%). The total number of drugs prescribed in the Medical Ward was 873 with an average of 5.70 drugs per prescription. Minimum drugs prescribed ranged from 2 drugs to a maximum of 12 drugs per prescription.

Table 3: Total number of patient and drugs.

Total No. of patient in hospital	Total No. of female patient, (%)	Total No. of male patient, (%)	Total No. of patient, (%)	Total No. of drugs prescribed (n)	Average drug prescribed per prescription
(ICU)					
225(100%)	27(12%)	45(20%)	72(32%)	549	7.625
(Medical ward)					
225(100%)	53(23.55%)	100(44.44%)	153(68%)	873	5.70

Drug-Drug Interactions based on severity:

Individual prescriptions of 72 patients were analyzed for drug-drug interaction in ICU. Among them 69(95.83%) patient's prescriptions carried DDIs. Total DDIs altogether (major, moderate, and minor interaction) were 523. There were 47(8.98%) major DDIs, 303(57.93%) moderate DDIs, and 173(33.07%) minor Drug Interactions out of 523(100%) interactions.

Similarly, DDIs were analyzed from the prescription of 153 inpatients of the Medical Ward. A total of 810 DDIs was found. Major DDIs were 54(6.18%), moderate interactions were 510(62.96%), and minor Interaction was 246(30.37%).

Moderate interaction was higher among major and minor interactions in both the ward. Student-T test was performed to compare moderate, minor and major DDIs. The p-value was statistically significant. P-value was significantly lower than <0.05 in both the ward.

Table 4: Drug-Drug Interactions based on severity:

Severity	No. of Drug-Drug Interactions (n) (%)	p-value <0.05
(ICU)(n=523)		
Major	47(8.98%)	
Moderate	303(57.93%)	
Minor	173(33.07%)	<0.05
(Medical Ward)(n=810)		
Major	54(6.67%)	
Moderate	510(62.96%)	
Minor	246(30.37%)	<0.05

Student-T test. P-value <0.05 compared with major, moderate and minor Drug-Drug Interaction.

Drug-Drug Interactions based on mechanism:

There were 523 DDIs in ICU out of which 175(33.46%) were pharmacokinetic Interaction. There were 183(34.99%) Pharmacodynamic DDIs and 165(31.54%) were unknown mechanisms causing DDIs. Similarly, in the Medical Ward, there were 810 DDIs out of which 369(45.55%) were Pharmacokinetic Interaction, 192(23.70%) were Pharmacodynamic Interactions and 249(30.74%) were of the unknown mechanism causing DDIs.

Statistical analysis showed a significant difference between pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic Interactions between various age groups in the Medical Ward whereas there was no significant difference between pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic Interaction in ICU.

Table 5: Drug-Drug Interactions based on mechanism:

Mechanism of Interactions	No. of Interactions	Percentage (%)	p-value
(ICU)(n=523)	175	33.46%	
Pharmacokinetic Drug-Drug Interactions:			
1.Absorption	64	12.23%	
2.Distribution:	2	0.38%	
3.Metabolism:	88	16.82%	
4.Excretion:	21	4.01%	
Pharmacodynamic Drug-Drug Interaction	183	34.99%	>0.05
Unknown mechanism	165	31.54%	
(Medical Ward)(n=810)			
Pharmacokinetic Drug-Drug Interactions:	369	45.55%	
1.Absorption:	145	17.9%	
2.Distribution:	3	0.37%	
3.Metabolism:	174	21.48%	
4.Excretion:	47	5.80%	
Pharmacodynamic Drug-Drug Interaction	192	23.70%	
Unknown mechanism	249	30.74%	<0.05

Distribution of Drug Interactions based on mechanism(PK and PD):

There were no significant differences with regard to the number of drug interactions (pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic) between the male and females in ICU and Medical Ward.

Table 6. Distribution of Drug Interactions based on mechanism(PK and PD):

Drug Interaction	Total Patients	Male	Female	p-Value <0.05
(ICU)				
Overall	72	45	27	
PK, n(%)	31(43.05)	18(40)	13(48.14)	>0.05
PD, n(%)	16(22.22)	11(24.44)	5(18.52)	
Unknown	25(34.72)	16(35.55)	9(33.33)	
(Medical Ward)				
Overall	153	100	53	
PK,n(%)	78(60)	51(51)	27(50.9)	>0.05
PD,n(%)	38(24.83)	25(25)	13(24.5)	
Unknown	37(24.18)	24(24)	13(24.5)	

Chi square test.

Drug-Drug Interaction based on organ system disorder:

There were more patients having cardiovascular and respiratory system diseases leading to the greatest number of DDIs in both the ward. There was an average of 10.6 DDIs per prescription in ICU for cardiovascular disease. Whereas there were an average of 7.64 DDIs per prescription in Medical Ward for Cardiovascular disease. These were highest the average DDIs in a prescription. Apart from cardiovascular and respiratory system disease in ICU Renal disease encountered a large number of DDIs.

Table 7: Drug-Drug Interaction based on organ system disorder:

Organ system disorder	Total number of drug interaction(n=1333)		Total No. of patients (n=225)		Average No. of Drug-Drug Interaction	
	ICU(n=523)(%)	Medical ward (n=810)(%)	ICU (n=72)	Medical ward (n=153)	ICU	Medical ward
Cardiovascular system	127(24.28%)	298(36.79%)	12	39	10.6	7.64
Respiratory system	97(18.54%)	189(23.33%)	10	27	9.7	7
Infectious disease	38(7.26%)	105(12.96%)	4	19	9.5	5.5
Renal system	58(11.08%)	48(5.92%)	6	11	9.67	4.36
Endocrine system	32(6.11%)	40(4.93%)	5	10	6.4	4
Gastro intestinal	30(5.73%)	29(3.58%)	5	8	6	3.6
Hematology	27(5.16%)	12(1.48%)	6	4	4.5	3
Gastrointestinal and alcoholic liver disease	40(7.64%)	35(4.32%)	7	13	5.71	2.69
Hepatic system	37(7.074%)	39(4.81%)	7	15	5.28	2.6
Nervous system	20(3.82%)	11(1.35%)	5	5	4	2.2
Musculoskeletal disease	17(3.25%)	4(0.49%)	5	2	3.4	2

Number of Drug-Drug Interactions per patients in ICU:

There were 27 patients experiencing an average of 4.77 DDIs per prescription. There were 34 patients experiencing an average of 8.97 DDIs per prescription and there were 11 patients experiencing an average of 8.09 DDIs per prescription.

Table 8: Number of Drug-Drug Interactions per patients in ICU:

Number of Drugs (ICU)	No. of patients (n=72)	No. of Drug Interaction (n=523), (%)	Average Number of DDIs with Number of Drugs in Prescription
5-10	27	129(24.6%)	4.77
10-15	34	305(58.31%)	8.97
>15	11	89(17%)	8.09

Number of Drug-Drug Interactions per patients in Medical ward:

There were 39 patients experiencing an average of 2 DDIs per prescription. There were 110 patients experiencing an average of 6.26 DDIs per prescription and there were 4 patients experiencing an average of 10.75 DDIs per prescription.

Table 9: Number of Drug-Drug Interactions per patients in Medical ward:

Number of Drugs (Medical Ward)	No. of patients (n=153)	No. of Drug Interaction (n=810), (%)	Average Number of DDIs with Number of Drugs in Prescription
2-5	39	78(9.6%)	2
6-10	110	689(85.06%)	6.26
>10	4	43(5.30%)	10.75

Management requirement for the Drug-Drug Interactions:

There were 1333 DDIs in the ICU and Medical Ward of the hospital. The dosage adjustment was the most needed intervention which was 16% followed by monitoring of drug level which was 15% among the Intervention in both the ward.

Table 10: Management requirement for the Drug-Drug Interactions:

Management	No. of Drug-Drug Interactions (n=1333) (%) ICU + Medical ward
Dosage Adjustment	213(15.97%)
Monitor for Drug level	199(14.93%)
No management required	186(13.95%)
Monitor for drug levels	134(10.05%)
Monitor for biochemical parameters	133(9.97%)
Change Dosing Interval	119(8.92%)
Avoid the combination	117(8.77%)
Monitor the electrolyte levels	80(6.001%)
Monitor the patient response	74(5.55%)
Monitor the sign and symptoms and biochemical parameter	45(3.37%)
Monitor the serum creatinine levels	33(2.47%)

DISCUSSION

DDIs is a matter of concern in the effective management of illness, it may pose a significant health hazard when interacting drug is not accurately estimated before prescribing¹⁸.

Our study found that there were more number of Drugs prescribed in ICU, with an average of 7.625 drugs per prescription compared with medical ward wherein 5.70 drugs per prescription were prescribed. Polypharmacy is the main cause of Drug Interaction (Mobina Tahmasebivand, 2020)¹⁹.

Our study estimated the prevalence of Drug-Drug interaction in medical ward and ICU. Our study found that among the 1333 interaction, 810 interaction were in Medical ward and 523 interaction were in ICU. Out of 810 interaction in medical ward, 45.55% were pharmacokinetic Interaction, 23.70% were pharmacodynamic Interaction and 30.74% were unknown Interaction. These findings were similar from the study reported in literature where Pharmacokinetic Interaction were dominant (Swathi Swaroopa Bora)²⁰.

Out of 523 interaction in ICU, 33.46% were Pharmacokinetic Interaction, 34.99% were pharmacodynamic Interaction and 31.54% were unknown Interaction. These findings were similar from the study reported in the literature where pharmacodynamic interaction were dominant in ICU (M Yulis Hamidy)²¹.

The severity assessment of DDIs in our study resulted in higher percentage of moderate DDIs in both the ICU and Medical ward of hospital. Moderate Interactions accounted for 57.93% in ICU followed by 33.07% minor and 8.98% major Interaction. Similarly, in Medical ward moderate interaction accounted for 62.96% followed by minor interaction of 30.37% and major drug interaction for 6.67%. These progression is similar to research published on Drug Interaction (Damboro and Kallgren,1998)²².

Cardiovascular and respiratory disease were most common. In our study we found that prescription of cardiovascular disease with cormorbid condition led to greatest average number of drug Interaction followed by respiratory disease. This result is similar to the finding from another study where cardiovascular disease had higher risk of drug interactions. The number of DDIs per patient was found to be increased from 24.6% to 58.31 % as the medication increased from ≤ 10 to ≤ 15 in ICU and similar was the case in medical ward where number of DDIs per patient increased from 9.6% to 85.06% as medication increased from ≤ 5 to ≤ 10 . This finding was similar to the report where the potential for drug interaction increased as the medication increased. (Goldberg et al. 1996)²³.

Our study found that the most common management of drug interaction was dose adjustment which accounted for 16% of total Drug Interaction, which was similar to the result reported by (Bergk et al. 2004)²⁴.

Apart from prescribed medication patient also intend over the counter medication, this adds the risk of DDIs. The alteration in pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic can be due to age and gene which are responsible factor for DDIs. The quality of life of patient can be altered due to DDIs and morbidity may be increased by DDIs. Hence careful use of medication and strict monitoring is required to avoid DDIs.

The clinical pharmacist intervened in ascertaining the DDIs along with using the electronic software in detecting the DDIs can alert higher percentage of clinically relevant DDIs²⁵.

Limitation of our study is this study was done at a tertiary care teaching hospital, where the prescription pattern may be different, compared with primary care settings. Another limitation is non prescription drugs were not taken in account.

CONCLUSION

Our study shows that a significant number of prescription had an average of 7.625 drugs prescribed in ICU where the predominant age group were elderly patient and an average of 5.70 drugs were prescribed in medical ward. Polypharmacy was the major reason for DDIs. Moderate DDIs were recorded highest among all the interaction. Our study helped in understanding the mechanism of DDIs, Disease condition and the intervention for DDIs. Our study suggest that clinical pharmacist intervention has a significant role in assessing and controlling DDIs.

Footnotes:

Funding:

This research receive no specific grants from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not for profit sectors.

Conflict of Interest statement:

The authors declares no conflict of interest.

Author's Contributions:

All authors have contributed significantly to research concept, literature review, objectives and design of the study.

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